

ted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]amino]benzoic acid, 2-[[[(4-substituted-phenyl)amino]thioxomethyl]hydrazides (4a–b). These compounds underwent cyclisation in presence of 2*N* NaOH to yield 5a–d which on reaction with different *N*-chloroacetylarylamines in presence of potassium carbonate yielded various novel title derivatives (6a–v) (Scheme 1).

Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of Substituted Indolyl-1,2,4-triazoles

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Manuscript received 8 February 1991,
accepted 5 August 1991

Scheme 1

COMPOUNDS bearing indole moiety are endowed with various biological activities¹. Triazoles which are biologically active compounds^{2,3} have not been so far linked with indole moiety. Thus with a view to gain further insight into the anti-convulsant activity of indole congeners, we have synthesised new substituted indolyl compounds incorporating triazole moiety at position-3 of the indole nucleus. The compounds were characterised by elemental analysis and spectral studies.

2-Substituted-indole-3-aldehyde (1a–b) on reaction with methyl 4-aminobenzoate in ethanol and acetic acid underwent condensation to yield methyl 4-[[[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]amino]benzoate (2a–b) which on reaction with hydrazine hydrate was converted into the corresponding hydrazides (3a–d). Reaction of the hydrazides with different aryl isothiocyanates yielded 4-[[[(2-substitu-

Experimental

The melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a JMS 300 spectrophotometer at 70 eV and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a EM 360 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Nitrogen analysis was performed on a Coleman N analyser 29 system.

2-Substituted-indol-3-carboxaldehyde⁴ (1a–b), 4-[[[(substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]amino]benzoates⁴ (2a–b) and 4-[[[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]aminobenzoic acid hydrazides⁵ (3a–b) were synthesised following the reported methods.

Preparation of 4a-d: A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) and different substituted aryl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in dry ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The contents were concentrated by distilling under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was washed several times with solvent ether and recrystallised from ethanol: 4b ν_{\max} 1 710 (C(O=)-NH), 1 050, 680 (C=S), 3 400 (NH) and 3 100 cm^{-1} (aromatic C-H); δ (CDCl_3) 4.8 (2H, s, NH-NH-C(S=)-NH), 4.4 (1H, s, NH-NH-C(S=)-NH), 8.0 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.8 (1H, s, NH indole) and 7.7-8.5 (12H, m, ArH) (Table 1).

3.7 (1H, br s, NH attached to CH_2), 8.0 (1H, s, N=CH), 9.1 (1H, s, indole NH) and 7.4-8.5 (18H, m, ArH); mol. ion m/z 528, 143 (219 benzene), 116 (148-HCN and $\text{CH}\equiv\text{CH}$), 117 (144-HCN), 91 (117-CN), 76 (91-NH), 65 (91-HCN), 120 (166-S= CH_2) and 77 (120-CONH). Similarly other compounds were synthesised (Table 1).

Biological studies I

Compounds 6a-v were evaluated *in vitro* for their enzyme inhibitory activity in albino rate (A) and *in vivo* for their anticonvulsant and analgesic activity in albino mice (B). The acute toxicity of compounds was assessed by determination of their approximate LD_{50} values.

In vitro studies: Adult albino rats (100-150 g) were killed by decapitation. The brain was homogenised in 0.25 M sucrose using Potter-Elvehjem homogeniser. The contents were chilled throughout the operation. The final volume of homogenate was 10% (w/v) of fresh tissue. Various enzymes inhibitory activities were determined using this preparation as a source of enzyme. For the determination of inhibitory activities, the compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol which did not have any inhibitory effect against the enzyme activities at a concentration used in the assay system. A suitable aliquot of the test solution was added so that the desired concentration in the final volume of reaction was obtained. The percent inhibition was calculated from the decrease observed in optical density.

The spectrophotofluorometric method of Kraji⁵ was used for the determination of monoamine oxidase (MAO) activity of the rat brain homogenate using kynuramine as substrate. The 4-hydroxyquinoline formed during oxidative deamination of kynuramine was measured fluorometrically in an Aminco-Bowman spectrophotofluorometer using activating light of 315 nm and measuring the fluorescence of 380 nm. The compounds were used at a final concentration of 1×10^{-4} M.

The inhibition of enzyme succinate dehydrogenase (SDH) activity was determined by spectrophotometric method as described by Slatter and Bonner⁶. Reduction of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ was measured in buffered medium (pH 7.2) in the presence of NaCN (which inhibits cytochrome oxidase) by monitoring the rate of decrease of optical density at 400 nm. Brain homogenate was the source of enzyme and sodium succinate was used as substrate. Compounds were used at the final concentration of 1×10^{-4} M.

In vivo studies: Anticonvulsant activity was determined⁷ against the pentylenetetrazol induced convulsions in albino mice of either sex (25-30 g). Compounds suspended in 5% gum acacia were injected intraperitoneally in a group of 10 animals at a dose of 100 mg/kg. Four hours after the administration of compounds the mice were injected with pentylenetetrazol (80 mg/kg s.c). The animals were observed for 60 min for the occurrence of seizures, a clonic spasm persisting at least 5 s was

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4-6*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %
4a	H	H	—	125	75
4b	H	4-Cl	—	115	70
4c	C ₆ H ₅	H	—	119	75
4d	C ₆ H ₅	4-Cl	—	80	75
5a	H	H	—	145	65
5b	H	4-Cl	—	219	60
5c	C ₆ H ₅	H	—	220	60
5d	C ₆ H ₅	4-Cl	—	118	65
6a	H	H	H	148	55
6b	H	H	2-CH ₃	174	60
6c	H	H	4-OCH ₃	107	65
6d	H	H	2-OCH ₃	112	50
6e	H	H	4-Cl	125	65
6f	H	H	3-Cl	106	60
6g	H	H	3-NO ₂	130	50
6h	H	4-Cl	H	134	65
6i	H	4-Cl	2-CH ₃	218	54
6j	H	4-Cl	4-OCH ₃	109	58
6k	H	4-Cl	2-OCH ₃	79	60
6l	H	4-Cl	4-Cl	135	55
6m	H	4-Cl	3-NO ₂	120	65
6n	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	91	50
6o	C ₆ H ₅	H	4-OCH ₃	101	60
6p	C ₆ H ₅	H	4-Cl	95	67
6q	C ₆ H ₅	H	3-Cl	86	58
6r	C ₆ H ₅	H	3-NO ₂	98	54
6s	C ₆ H ₅	4-Cl	H	118	60
6t	C ₆ H ₅	4-Cl	2-OCH ₃	99	65
6u	C ₆ H ₅	4-Cl	4-Cl	102	60
6v	C ₆ H ₅	4-Cl	3-NO ₂	106	55

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Preparation of 5a-d: Compounds 4a-d in 2N NaOH were refluxed on a wire guage for 4 h, then cooled, filtered and the filtrate was acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solids were washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol: ν_{\max} 5a 1 640 (C=N), 2 565 (SH) and 1 050, 700 cm^{-1} (C-S); m/z 395, 362 (M-S-H), 259 (362-C₆H₅NC), 245 (259-N), 231 (259-N₂), 291 (245-CN), 143 (219-C₆H₅) and 92 (119-CH \equiv CH) (Table 1).

Preparation of 6a-v: A mixture of 5a-d (0.01 mol), N-chloroacetylarylamines (0.01 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.01 mol) was refluxed in dry acetone for 6 h. It was then filtered hot and the filtrate poured dropwise into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed several times with water and recrystallised from ethanol: 6a ν_{\max} 1 645 (C=N), 1 700 (C=O), 1 140, 750 (C-S) and 3 350 cm^{-1} (NH); δ (CDCl_3) 2.6 (2H, d, CH₂NH),

considered a threshold convulsion. Animals not exhibiting even a threshold convulsion during 60 min were considered protected. The number of animals protected in each group was recorded and anticonvulsant activity was represented as percent protection.

Morphine-like analgesic activity was tested⁸ by the mouse tail pinch method. Compounds injected i.p. in 5% aqueous suspension of gum acacia at a dose of 100 mg/kg. Four hours after the administration of compounds, an artery clip with branches enclosed in a thin rubber tube was applied to the root of the tail of a mouse for 30 s. The animals made continuous attempts to remove the noxious stimulus by biting the clip. The insensitivity to the noxious stimulus was taken as the positive response and the results were expressed as percentage of mice showing analgesic activity. Morphine hydrochloride was used as a reference standard for comparing the effective analgesic property of these compounds.

Approximate lethal dose (ALD₅₀)⁹ of the compounds was determined in albino mice. The animals were divided into group of 4 each and were fasted for 18 h prior to the drug administration. The compounds were given in a dose of 600, 800, 1000 and 1400 mg/kg intraperitoneally and 24 h mortality was recorded.

Results and Discussion

Among compounds 6, all except h, j and r afforded rat brain monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibition ranging from 4.2 to 100%. Maximum inhibition of 100% was exhibited by compounds k, l and m having chloro substituent at *para*-position of phenyl ring attached at position-4 of the triazole nucleus as R₃ and by compound 6n in which position-2 of the indole ring was occupied by phenyl group. Further, 6i having methyl substituent at position-2 of the phenyl ring as R₃ exhibited promising enzyme inhibitory activities as compared to other methyl substituted analogue in which position-4 of the triazole nucleus was occupied by chloro substituent. Incorporation of phenyl group at position-2 of the indole ring caused a decrease in inhibition except compound 6n where 100% inhibition was observed. Moreover, derivatives, having methoxy group produced moderate enzyme inhibitory activity.

Maximum SDH inhibition was shown by compound 6n (50%) having electron-withdrawing chloro and nitro substituents present at different positions in the phenyl ring as R₂ and R₃ while compound 6g having nitro substituent at position-3 of the phenyl ring as R₃ showed minimum (2.6%) SDH inhibition. Further, compound having unsubstituted phenyl ring at 1-, 2- and 4-positions of triazole nucleus exhibited 40% inhibition while derivatives in which position-3 of the triazole nucleus was occupied by different electron-releasing and electron-withdrawing substituents and position-2 of the indole

ring was unsubstituted, caused a decrease in enzyme inhibitory activity (6b-g, 2.6-24.6%).

Maximum protection (100%) was afforded by compound 6q having phenyl group at position-2 of the indole moiety and chloro substituent at position-3 of the phenyl ring as R₃, whereas compound 6g in which nitro substituted phenyl ring was present at position-3 of the triazole nucleus showed no anticonvulsant activity. Further, introduction of chloro group at position-4 of the phenyl ring as R₃ exhibited 60% protection (6e, l, q and u). Similar effect was also observed in unsubstituted triazole derivative (6a) while replacement of chloro substituent from *para*- to *meta*-position caused a substantial decrease in protective ability (6f, 20%) except compound 6q which produced maximum anticonvulsant activity. Methoxy substituted derivatives exhibited moderate activity against seizure (cf compound 6c, d, j, o and t, 40-50%) except 6k where anticonvulsant activity decreased to 20%.

All the compounds showed analgesic activity in the range 10-80%. Maximum analgesic activity (80%) was shown by compounds 6e, l, o and s in which phenyl ring at position-3 of the triazole nucleus at R₃ was either unsubstituted or substituted with methoxy or chloro substituents. Moreover presence of methoxy substituents as R₃ in phenyl substituted indole ring was proved more effective in producing analgesia (6o, 80%; 6t, 60%) as compared to derivatives in which indole ring was unsubstituted (6c, d, j and k, 40%). Methyl substituted derivatives (6b, i) produced only 20% analgesic activity.

In the toxicity study, 100% mortality was shown by compound 6g, 80% by 6d, h-k and r, 60% by 6a, c, e, m and s, 50% by 6o and 20-40% by rest of the compounds.

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